

Selectivity Characteristics of Montmorillonite Clay

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Exchange reactions have been carried out between varying amounts of H-resin and varying concentrations of montmorillonite clays saturated with Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} and Ba^{++} ions in aqueous medium and the selectivity coefficients have been calculated. The selectivity coefficients decrease with the increase in concentration of the clay suspension. The decrease is most prominent in the case of K-saturated clay. The selectivity coefficient probably depends on the relative affinities of the ions towards the solid exchangers. The decrease in selectivity coefficient with clay concentration is attributed to the overlapping of electrical double layer and subsequent immobilization of ions.

The isotherms obtained with the varying amounts of H-resin are somewhat reversed in shape to ordinary adsorption isotherms

To ascertain the role of ionic hydration the experiments have also been carried out in 50% aqueous-ethanolic medium and the decrease in selectivity coefficient is found to be more prominent. The somewhat low values of the selectivity coefficient of Na^+ and K^+ ions in ethanolic medium are probably due to the low dielectric constant of the medium.

The reversible nature of ion-exchange reactions has led many workers¹ to use the law of Mass Action to characterize the exchange behaviour of solid exchangers like synthetic resins and clays. The distribution of ions between the solid exchangers having the ions associated with them will obviously depend on the relative abundance of the ions and their relative affinities towards the exchangers. The complicating effects of complex formation in the solution may be avoided by using two solid exchangers either in direct contact with each other or immersing one of the exchangers in the suspension of the other. The selectivity coefficient or selectivity number is calculated by dividing the ratio of the concentrations raised to appropriate powers of the two ions involved in the exchange reaction in one phase to that in the other (*vide* equations 3 & 4). It is thus simply the equilibrium constant of the reversible exchange reactions, such as:

between uni-univalent ions, and

between uni-bivalent ions.

1. Basu, Seal, and Mukherjee, —*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 71.
2. Marshall and Garza, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1959, 63, 1663.

The equilibrium constants can be represented as usual by :

$$K_A^B = \frac{[B^+]_R \cdot [A^+]_M}{[A^+]_R \cdot [B^+]_M} = \frac{[B^+]_R/[A^+]_R}{[B^+]_M/[A^+]_M} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$K_D^C = \frac{[C^{n+}]_R \cdot [D^+]_M}{[D^+]_R \cdot [C^{n+}]_M} = \frac{[C^{n+}]_R/[D^+]_R}{[C^{n+}]_M/[D^+]_M} \quad \dots$$

$$K_D^C = \frac{[C^{n+}]_R^{\frac{1}{n}} [D^+]_M}{[D^+]_R [C^{n+}]_M^{\frac{1}{n}}} = \frac{[C^{n+}]_R^{\frac{1}{n}}/[D^+]_R}{[C^{n+}]_M^{\frac{1}{n}}/[D^+]_M} = \sqrt[n]{K_D^C} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where the expressions in parenthesis denote concentration and subscripts R and M denote the two solid exchanger phases viz synthetic resin exchanger and montmorillonite clay respectively. These quantities are also termed as Selectivity Coefficients.

The Selectivity Coefficients obtained either with one ion in solid exchanger and the other ion in solution or with both the ions being present as exchangeable ions in the solid exchangers, is not expected to be constant when concentrations are used in place of activity³, although some of the workers have claimed it to be so.

In the present work a suspension of an exchange resin in its hydrogen form is taken in a cellophane bag to simulate the exchanging surface of the plant roots and the exchange of ions from the homoionic clays saturated with different ions for hydrogen ions of the resin has been measured. From these experimental results the Selectivity Coefficients have been calculated. To simulate the soil-plant root condition as far as possible the clay used has been varied from a dilute sol to a paste. In order to ascertain the role of hydration on the exchange behaviour of ions ethanolic-aqueous media have been used.^{5,6}

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrogen clay was prepared by the usual way from a black cotton soil Padegaan B-type and Akli bentonite.

Na⁺, K, NH₄⁺ and Ba-clays were prepared by adding requisite quantities of the corresponding hydroxide to suspensions of hydrogen clay and then equilibrating for some time. Ca²⁺ and Mg-clays were prepared by adding calculated amounts of chemically pure solid calcium carbonate and magnesium oxide respectively to hydrogen clay suspensions.

Akli bentonite was used for preparing all the base saturated clays in aqueous media except Ba-clay which was prepared from Padegaan B-type. In ethanolic media, however, akli bentonite was used to prepare K- and Ca-saturated clays only and the rest were prepared from the black cotton soil.

3. Duncan and Lister, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3285.

4. Kressman and Kitchener, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190, 1201, 1208.

5. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian Soc., Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2.

6. Chatterjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1950, 7, 37.

Amberlite IR-100 was converted into the H-form by repeated treatment with hydrochloric acid. It was washed with distilled water and dried at 105°C.

The experimental technique for the study of exchange between the hydrogen resin and base-saturated clays at different concentrations, using both aqueous and 50% ethanolic media, was described by Chatterjee in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*).

The selectivity coefficients, $K_{M^+}^{M^{2+}}$ and $K_{M^+}^{N^+}$ where M^+ denotes Na^+ , K^+ , and NH_4^+ and M^{2+} denotes Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Ba^{2+} are calculated from the exchange data and given in Table I. Table II contains the results of similar experiments done in ethanolic medium (51.0%).

On the basis of the exchange reaction as written (P-1), higher values of the selectivity coefficients indicate greater adsorbability of the metal ions on the resin exchanger than the clay and *vice-versa*.

TABLE I

Selectivity coefficients of base saturated clays for hydrogen resin in aqueous medium

	Form of clay	Concentration of clay g/100 gs. sol.	Selectivity coefficients corresponding to symmetry values of added cations.			
			0.5B	1.0B	1.5B	2.0B
1	Na	1.71	0.64	0.40	0.58	1.90
		3.80	.58	.33	.57	0.74
		5.52	.51	.35	.47	.88
2	K	1.71	1.90	1.80	1.40	1.60
		3.58	1.30	1.13	1.20	1.20
		5.00	0.60	0.40	1.03	0.90
		1.16	0.12	0.10	0.48	0.68
3	NH_4	3.32	.06	.11	.24	.40
		4.00	.024	.08	.23	.36
		1.84	.04	.056	.15	.44
4	Ca	3.07	.016	.041	.084	.20
		5.70	.006	.012	.021	.021
		1.29	.02	.26	.16	.14
5	Mg	2.68	.26	.15	.07	.046
		5.16	.085	.077	.031	.025
6	Ba	1.11	.07	.26	.34	.40
7	Ba	2.22	.16	.15	.16	.088
		4.44	.13	.07	.088	.087

TABLE II

Selectivity coefficients of base saturated clays for hydrogen resin in 50% ethanolic medium

	From of clay	Concentration of clay g/100 gm. sol.	Selectivity coefficient corresponding to symmetry values of added cations.			
			0.5S	1.0S	1.5S	2.0S
1	Na	1.83	0.14	0.19	0.18	0.32
		3.66	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.06
		4.84	0.040	0.046	0.049	0.041
2	K	0.78	1.70	1.50	1.40	7.70
		1.16	0.33	0.31	0.30	0.63
		2.32	0.06	0.066	0.067	0.076
3	NH ₄	1.23	0.31	0.25	0.25	0.56
		2.45	0.18	0.10	0.28	0.34
		5.14	0.10	0.13	0.19	0.20
4	Ca	0.85	0.20	0.01	0.04	0.40
		1.70	0.08	0.12	0.05	0.05
		2.55	0.13	0.035	0.022	0.011
5.	Mg	1.10	0.90	0.55	0.38	0.17
		2.20	0.55	0.29	0.12	0.08
		4.40	0.34	0.06	0.053	0.03
6.	Ba	1.11	0.67	0.25	0.18	0.19
		2.22	0.19	0.086	0.04	0.05
		4.44	0.07	0.03	0.017	0.017

DISCUSSION

The nature of variation of Selectivity Coefficients of the ions with clay concentration and also with the amount of resin, i.e., the concentration of H⁺ ion in the resin phase, is shown in Fig. 1. The amounts of H-resin have been expressed in terms of symmetry concentration in the Tables. Fig. 2 represents the results of the same experiments done in 50% aqueous ethanolic medium.

The selectivity coefficient of K⁺ ion uniformly decreases sharply with increasing clay concentration and the rate is greater at low symmetry concentrations of the resin used. The Selectivity Coefficients of NH₄ ion and the bivalent ions show similar variations with the concentration of clay suspension, the rates of decrease being much less than with K⁺ ion but still greater in the region of low clay concentration. With Na⁺ ion the picture is somewhat different. Except in the case of the system using 2.05 H-resin the decrease in Selectivity Coefficient is very small. The decrease of Selectivity Coefficient with increasing clay concentration may be attributed to the overlapping of the double layer and subsequent "immobilization" of ions¹⁴. On the basis of the above hypothesis, the small decrease in the case of Na⁺ ion is perhaps due to the prevention of overlapping as a result of considerable hydration of sodium ions.

Marshall⁷ has discussed the observed variation of mean bonding energy of various ions as a function of clay concentration, in terms of the behaviour of an ion in the resultant electrical fields as two charged particles are brought nearer.

It is expected that the increased dissociation at low clay concentration will be reduced at high clay concentration. Slightly dissociated ions would be expected to show maximum in free cation-bonding energy and hence a minimum Selectivity Coefficient.

The Selectivity Coefficients were plotted against the symmetry concentration of H-resin. The curves for Na^+ and K^+ ions at low clay concentration show an initial decrease followed by an increase up to the symmetry concentration studied. At higher concentration of clays a further decrease in Selectivity Coefficient values is observed. The Selectivity Coefficients of NH_4^+ and Ca^{2+} ions show increase with symmetry concentration but in case of Ca^{2+} the rate of increase is less sharp than NH_4^+ . Ba^{2+} at low clay concentration resembles Na^+ but at high clay concentration the selectivity values are almost constant.

In ethanolic-aqueous media (*vide* Fig. 2), the ionic hydrations are reduced so that the overlapping of the double layers as the clay becomes concentrated is more pronounced. Consequently, the variation of the Selectivity Coefficients are, relative to pure aqueous media, sharper with the changes in both the clay and resin contents of the respective suspensions. Otherwise, the relative positions of the ions remain the same.

The low values of the Selectivity Coefficient of the Na^+ and K^+ ions in ethanolic media are probably due to the low dielectric constant of the media.

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